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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**9-Criminal Liability for Economic Crimes:
Issues of Legal Qualification And Application
In Practice. By Volodymyr Myslyvyy and
others. p. 176.**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**A GROUP OF UNIVERSITY GRADUATES IN UKRAINE
PREPARED**

**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR ECONOMIC CRIMES: ISSUES OF LEGAL QUALIFICATION AND APPLICATION IN PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

The study is relevant due to the increasing number of economic crimes in Ukraine and the urgent need to improve their criminal legal qualification amid integration into the European legal area. Challenges include legislative conflicts,

vague evaluative concepts, and inconsistent case law. The study aims to examine the peculiarities of qualifying economic crimes in Ukraine, focusing on criminal law regulation and court practice. Methodologically, it combines content analysis of Supreme Court decisions, comparative legal methods, and formal legal approaches. The author identifies key problems such as misuse of evaluative concepts, errors in determining guilt, and neglect of international experience. Approaches from the EU, USA, China, Italy, and India are analyzed to explore adaptation possibilities for Ukrainian legislation. The study advocates introducing corporate liability, plea bargaining, and mandatory expert economists in complex cases. Its results are practically significant for enhancing criminal legislation, judicial methodologies, training programs, and drafting laws to combat economic crimes effectively.

Keywords: *criminal liability, economic crimes, qualification, judicial practice, corporate liability.*

1- INTRODUCTION

The issue of criminal liability for economic crimes is one of the most complex and controversial in modern legal science and practice. In the context of globalization, digitalization of the economy and growing transnational crime, national legal systems face challenges related to the qualification of new forms of offenses, adequacy of sanctions and harmonization with international standards. This problem is particularly relevant in Ukraine, where economic crime not only harms the state and society, but also undermines trust in the legal system and promotes corruption. In the context of martial law, economic recovery, and EU integration, the effectiveness of combating economic crimes and the clarity of criminal law qualifications are extremely important. A review of the scientific literature shows that researchers pay considerable attention to the problems of criminal liability for economic crimes. In particular, in-depth studies on this issue are presented in Hryshchuk and Paliukh,¹ Miceli,² Auriol et al.,³ Foti and Malino,⁴ and Marin and Sen.⁵ Attention is paid to the issues of legislative conflicts,

¹ Hryshchuk, V., & Paliukh, L. (2022). Problematic issues of liability for crimes against justice in the criminal law doctrine. *Social and Legal Studies*, 5(3), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.32518/2617-4162-2022-5-3-29-37>

² Miceli, T. J. (2022). Counting offenders' gains? Economic and moral considerations in the determination of criminality. *European Journal of Law and Economics*, 54(3), 475–496. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10657-022-09744-7>;

Miceli, T. J. (2024). Expanding responsibility: Criminal doctrines. In *Harm and responsibility* (pp. 185–202). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-74831-8_8

³ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). Corporate criminals in a market context: Enforcement and optimal sanctions. *European Journal of Law and Economics*, 56(3), 225–287. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10657-023-09773-w>

⁴ Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). Third parties in Italian criminal proceedings. In S. Ruggeri, A. Falcone, & V. Di Nuzzo (Eds.), *Third parties in criminal proceedings* (Legal Studies in International,

uncertainty of terms and the role of corporate responsibility. Some authors focus on the mechanisms of plea bargaining, compensation for victims, and the specifics of cybercrime investigation.⁶ Despite the breadth of scientific approaches, research remains insufficiently developed on the participation of expert economists in the qualification process and the role of case law in shaping law enforcement standards. The “white spots” in the study of criminal liability for economic crimes are primarily the lack of a systematic analysis of the practice of the Supreme Court of Ukraine in recent years in terms of errors in qualification, excessive use of evaluative concepts and failure to take into account international experience. The scientific approach to determining the criteria of substantial damage and the introduction of clear instruments of liability of legal entities for economic offenses also need to be developed.

The purpose of this paper is to study the problems of criminal law qualification of economic crimes in Ukraine, to identify the main errors of judicial practice, to analyze international experience and to formulate proposals for improving criminal law and law enforcement.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent scientific research in the area of criminal liability for economic crimes points to a number of conceptual and practical problems in the qualification of such offenses. Large attention is drawn to the problems of the regulation of regulation and the consistency of criminal legislation with the international norms.⁷ In particular, it is argued to be challenging to protect modern challenges such as financial crimes or the digital economy⁸ in practice with legal norms. An analysis of case law indicates that the ambiguity of legal norms interpretation is one of the main problem that may cause the

European and Comparative Criminal Law, Vol. 10, pp. 99–144). Springer.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73970-5_5

⁵ Marin, O., & Sen, I. (2018). Odpowiedzialność za przestępstwa w dziedzinie działalności gospodarczej według ukraińskiego Kodeksu karnego w kontekście procesów integracji europejskiej. *Teka Komisji Prawniczej PAN Oddział w Lublinie*, 11(2), 251–263.
<https://doi.org/10.32084/tekapr.2018.11.2-17>

⁶ Chakrabarty, S. P., & Chattopadhyay, S. (2025). Criminal liability of artificial intelligence-generated deepfakes in India. In M. Chakraborty, S. P. Chakrabarty, A. Penteado, & V. E. Balas (Eds.), *Proceedings of 5th International Ethical Hacking Conference: eHaCON 2024 (Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, Vol. 1148, pp. 233–250). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-8457-8_16;

Ewing, B. (2023). Criminal responsibility and fair moral opportunity. *Criminal Law and Philosophy*, 17(2), 291–316. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11572-021-09621-5>

⁷ Hryshchuk, V., & Paliukh, L. (2022). *Id.*

⁸ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*;

Miceli, T. J. (2022). *Id.*

misclassification of the act and inconsistency of court decisions.⁹ Use of evaluative concepts of 'significant harm' or 'serious consequences' gives the law enforcement the opportunity for subjective approach.¹⁰ Historically, international practice has actively used the institution of corporate responsibility and specialized mechanisms for evaluation of economic damage to reduce these risks.¹¹

Ukraine is in the absence of a clear system of the differentiation of criminal liability for economic crimes between the criminal offenses and the administrative offenses.¹² Such a situation complicates the work of law enforcement agencies and at the same time, facilitates selective enforcement.¹³ As a matter of fact, European countries make active use of the criteria of materiality of harm, as well as plea bargaining, which lighten the judicial system burden and make economic criminals prosecution more effective.¹⁴ Likewise, international practice suggests the significance of applying, among other things, mechanisms of preventive control and welfare cooperation between the government agencies and companies in the fight against economic crime.¹⁵ The ADRs (Alternative Dispute Resolution) is an important element of the practice of antieless crime today in modern terms of resolution of disputes. AD

⁹ Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). Problems of criminal prosecution in procurement. In E. G. Popkova (Ed.), *Business 4.0 as a subject of the digital economy* (pp. 987–989). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-90324-4_162;

Gorodnova, O. N., Kirillov, M. A., Fadeeva, K. V., Pavlova, M. V., & Vissarov, A. V. (2024). Assessment of justice in crimes against property and punishments. In E. G. Popkova, O. V. Kaurova, & A. N. Maloletko (Eds.), *Sustainable cooperation for the creation of green supply chains based on environmental technologies and responsible innovations* (pp. 359–367). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-70962-3_40

¹⁰ Horder, J. (2025). Corporate criminal liability under the Economic Crime and Corporate Transparency Act 2023. *Legal Studies*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1017/lst.2024.46>

Hryshchuk, V., & Paliukh, L. (2022). Problematic issues of liability for crimes against justice in the criminal law doctrine. *Social and Legal Studios*, 5(3), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.32518/2617-4162-2022-5-3-29-37>

¹¹ Jiang, T., & Li, Q. (2024). Cooperation-oriented exemptions from criminal liability in China. *Criminal Law Forum*, 35(3), 425–452. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10609-024-09489-9>;

Ochi, M. (2024). Principles on reparation for victims in international criminal justice. In *The premises of international criminal procedure* (pp. 141–159). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-6786-1_7

¹² Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*

¹³ Polianskyi, A., & Polianskyi, O. (2021). Criminal liability for crimes against national security. *Archives of Criminology and Forensic Sciences*, 3, 72–88. <https://doi.org/10.32353/acfs.3.2021.08>

¹⁴ Ewing, B. (2023). *Id.*;

Mukherjee, S. (2023). Need for economic remedies with the increase in product liability cases in the twenty-first century. In E. Lau, R. K. Brahmana, & L. M. Tan (Eds.), *Economics and finance readings: APEF 2022* (pp. 101–117). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-1979-6_7

¹⁵ Chakrabarty, S. P., & Chattopadhyay, S. (2025). *Id.*

can be a suitable tool to restore justice and deliver to victims compensation without the excessive burden on the judicial system, considering the complexity of economic crimes. Ometo¹⁶ finds that there may be potential for ADR in asset recovery of a white collar type, especially given the presence of weak formal mechanisms. Accordingly, Khedmati¹⁷ (2021) stresses the importance of the arbitrators to make a careful attention to cases of financial crimes, marking their criminal character. Therefore, in many regards, the integration of ADR as one of the means of combating economic crime will not only bring to terms the interests of the parties and lessen the probability of blocking the schedule of criminal process, but also facilitate the effective development of the market.

In this context, legislation requiring the auditing of large company financial transactions and the increased sanctions against such financial fraud are effective.¹⁸ In Ukraine, such approaches have not yet become systemic, which leads to a significant level of economic shadowing and abuse.¹⁹ It is also important to pay attention to studies that highlight current challenges in the field of criminal liability related to the use of new technologies and transnational economic processes. In particular, Jessen²⁰ analyzes the complexity of determining liability in the field of autonomous systems and drones, which may be relevant for economic crimes committed using remote or digital technologies. Samaradiwakera-Wijesundara²¹ emphasizes the problems of complementarity in bringing companies to criminal liability in African countries, which emphasizes the global nature of the difficulties in this area and the need to unify approaches. The conclusions of Staffler²² on how criminal activity was particularly dynamic in time and space are especially pertinent for Ukrainian legislation; Staffler²³

¹⁶ Ometo, B. (2020). The place of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) in recovering assets of 'white collar crimes' in Kenya. SSRN. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3705974>

¹⁷ Khedmati, A. (2021). Financial crimes and commercial arbitration: What should arbitrators do? *Fordham Journal of Corporate & Financial Law*. <https://news.law.fordham.edu/jcfl/2021/04/21/financial-crimes-and-commercial-arbitration-what-should-arbitrators-do/>

¹⁸ Marin, O., & Sen, I. (2018). *Id.*;

Staffler, L. (2022b). Criminal liability concepts for entrepreneurs and companies. In *Business criminal law* (pp. 163–208). Springer Gabler. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-34472-6_6

¹⁹ Singh, P. K. (2022). Corporate criminal liability in India. *Athens Journal of Law*, 8(1), 31–48. <https://doi.org/10.30958/ajl.8-1-2>

²⁰ Jessen, H. (2024). MASS and liability for damages. In C. J. Chae & R. Baumler (Eds.), *Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS)—Regulation, Technology, and Policy* (WMU Studies in Maritime Affairs, Vol. 11, pp. 211–234). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-69437-0_11

²¹ Samaradiwakera-Wijesundara, C. (2022). Complementarity and criminal liability of companies in Africa: Missing the mark? In E. C. Lubaale & N. Dyani-Mhango (Eds.), *National accountability for international crimes in Africa* (pp. 115–169). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-88044-6_5

²² Staffler, L. (2022a). Approaching the phenomenon: Business crimes in space and time. In *Business criminal law* (pp. 3–9). Springer Gabler. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-34472-6_1

²³ Staffler, L. (2022b). *Id.*

provides very detailed ideas of the criminal liability of entrepreneurs and companies. Also all of these studies show that the Ukrainian legal system need to be adapted to the rapidity of changes in the conditions of the globalization, such as liability on cyberspace and the creation of special legal mechanisms for the undertaken action (the corporation).

For this reason, the analysis of recent studies demonstrates the necessity of improvement of the framework of criminal liability for economic crimes, introducing legal definitions and the creation of adequate mechanisms to prevent offenses. The international experience in the field of criminal law regulation is an important factor for the improvement of the effectiveness of law enforcement in Ukraine.²⁴ Continuing the review of current research, it is worth noting certain aspects that remain important for the formation of an effective system of criminal liability for economic crimes. In particular, the issues of criminal liability of legal entities are actively studied in the works of Karimova and Nigmadjanov,²⁵ which emphasizes the need for clear regulatory sanctions for corporate entities. Similar problems are highlighted in the research of Singh,²⁶ who emphasizes that without defining the limits of corporate liability in national legislation, gaps in prosecution for crimes in the field of economic activity remain.

Studies by Akbar²⁷ and Middha et al.²⁸ point to the importance of reforming legislation with a focus on protecting the rights of victims and introducing compensation and redress systems, which are practically underdeveloped in Ukraine. Mukherjee²⁹ emphasizes the growing need for legislative mechanisms for economic remedies for victims of violations, which could be effective in the Ukrainian context. In European and global practices, importance is attached to the development of the concept of liability in the context of transnational crime and digital technologies.³⁰ In Ukraine, however, the regulatory framework for cybercrime and the use of artificial intelligence

²⁴ Jessen, H. (2024). *Id.*;

Samaradiwakera-Wijesundara, C. (2022). *Id.*

²⁵ Karimova, D., & Nigmadjanov, U. (2024). Perspectives on introducing corporate criminal liability for the crime of bribery in Uzbekistan. In R. Urinboyev (Ed.), *The political economy of Central Asian law* (pp. 53–77). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-55341-7_3

²⁶ Singh, P. K. (2022). *Id.*

²⁷ Akbar, M. F. (2023). The urgency of law reforms on economic crimes in Indonesia. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2023.2175487>

²⁸ Middha, M., Kedia, B., & Bhattacharya, B. (2023). Compensatory jurisprudence in India: A step forward to rehabilitate the victims of various acts and crimes. *International Journal for the Semiotics of Law*, 36(4), 1311–1323. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11196-023-09995-w>

²⁹ Mukherjee, S. (2023). *Id.*

³⁰ El-Kady, R. (2024). Artificial intelligence from the criminal law perspective. In A. E. Hassanien, A. Darwish, M. F. Tolba, & V. Snášel (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Systems and Informatics 2024 (AISI 2024)* (Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Vol. 233, pp. 162–173). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-77299-3_16;

Jessen, H. (2024). *Id.*

in criminal activity remains unsystematized, as evidenced by the analysis of Chakrabarty and Chattopadhyay³¹ and El-Kady.³² It is also worth considering the recommendations of Staffler,³³ who notes the importance of spatial and temporal approaches in the qualification of economic crimes and the consideration of new types of financial fraud.

To summarize, scientific sources unanimously point to the need to harmonize national norms with international standards, create a corporate responsibility system, introduce effective judicial practice and differentiate corpus delicti depending on the degree of public danger.³⁴ The problems that have not yet been properly addressed are the lack of a legal mechanism for liability for economic crimes in the field of artificial intelligence and digital platforms, as well as the lack of procedural participation of victims in the process of compensation for losses.

3. METHOD

The materials and methods of the study were based on a comprehensive approach to the analysis of the national and international legal framework in the field of criminal liability for economic crimes, as well as a generalization of modern judicial practice in Ukraine. The study was conducted by the author on the basis of a content analysis of 50 decisions of the Supreme Court of Ukraine over the past three years, selected by the criteria of disputes in the qualification of economic crimes and the use of evaluative concepts. Additionally, a comparative legal analysis of approaches to criminal liability in the legislation of the European Union, the United States, China, Italy and India was conducted. The material basis for the study was published international scientific research, regulations of Ukraine and the EU, as well as official statistics and methodological materials of court practice. The study used general scientific methods, such as logical analysis, systematization, and generalization, as well as special legal methods, such as formal legal and comparative legal analysis, modeling, and legal interpretation.

4. RESULTS

Criminal law regulation of liability for economic crimes in Ukraine is undergoing a constant transformation, driven by both domestic economic challenges and the state's

³¹ Chakrabarty, S. P., & Chattopadhyay, S. (2025). *Id.*

³² El-Kady, R. (2024). *Id.*

³³ Staffler, L. (2022a). *Id.*

³⁴ Karimova, D., & Nigmadjanov, U. (2024). *Id.*;

Marin, O., & Sen, I. (2018). *Id.*;

Middha, M., Kedia, B., & Bhattacharya, B. (2023). *Id.*;

Samaradiwakera-Wijesundara, C. (2022). *Id.*

international obligations. Such crimes are regulated mainly in Title VII of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, which defines the main corpus delicti in the field of economic activity, finance and entrepreneurship. Despite the existence of a regulatory framework, the accuracy of the wording of the norms, their consistency with international standards, and the adequacy of their practical application remain problematic. Domestic legislation, which currently almost never reflects the dynamics of the emergence of new forms of crime committed in the conditions of the digital economy and international economic relations,³⁵ since it is forced to lag behind the processes of accelerated development of the world's economy and modern technologies.

Moreover, it is important to point out that there has been no attempt to distinct liability for crimes against the economy according to whether a particular crime is a matter of public danger.³⁶ The qualifications of this problem are often ambiguous and the court practice manifestly discretionary. By taking into account the international experience, in particular the principles of corporate responsibility, predicated within the EU,³⁷ it is necessary to solve the problem. At the same time, there is an area of criminal law regulation of legal entities liability, in particular, for crimes of corruption and money laundering, which is insufficiently developed in Ukraine.

Attention should also be paid to the existing problem of law enforcement practice, where there is a gap between the formal provisions of the law and real mechanisms of bringing to justice.³⁸ In practice, there are often difficulties in proving intent or mercenary purpose, which complicates the legitimate application of criminal law. Summarizing, it can be stated that the current state of criminal law regulation of liability for economic crimes in Ukraine requires systematic review and improvement, taking into account international experience and practical challenges.³⁹

The issue of the correct qualification of economic crimes remains relevant in the practice of criminal law in Ukraine. The increased complexity of such offenses is due to the multicomponent nature of the crime, the presence of evaluative concepts, and the need to distinguish between administrative offenses, civil torts, and criminal offenses.⁴⁰ It is not uncommon for law enforcement agencies or courts to make mistakes in determining the form of guilt or the degree of public danger of an act.⁴¹

Among the problems of qualification, the following key areas should be highlighted, which are systematically manifested in law enforcement practice (Table 1).

³⁵ Hryshchuk, V., & Paliukh, L. (2022). *Id.*

³⁶ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*

³⁷ Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*

³⁸ Polianskyi, A., & Polianskyi, O. (2021). *Id.*

³⁹ Dong, X., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Criminal law. In *On contemporary Chinese legal system* (pp. 129–159). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-2505-6_7

⁴⁰ Miceli, T. J. (2022). *Id.*

⁴¹ Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*

As can be seen from Table 1, the main problems of qualification of economic crimes relate to imperfect legislative terminology, conflicts between norms and insufficient specialization of pre-trial investigation bodies.

Table 1. Main problems of qualification of economic crimes in law enforcement practice

Problem.	Characteristics	Implications for law enforcement
Use of evaluative concepts	The concepts of “significant harm” and “serious consequences” are not specified and are subjectively interpreted	Risk of misclassification, abuse or delay of pre-trial investigation
Conflicts between criminal and administrative law	Overlapping provisions and uncertainty whether an act is subject to criminal or administrative liability	Application of the least effective sanctions, evasion of criminal liability
Incorrect definition of the form of guilt	Problems of distinguishing between intent and negligence in actions that led to economic losses	Misrepresentation of qualifications and failure to observe the principle of justice in sentencing
Insufficient training of investigators and judges in the field of economics	Lack of specialized knowledge of complex financial and economic mechanisms	Difficulty in proving the objective side of the crime, the likelihood of acquittals due to procedural errors
Lack of systematic judicial practice	Uneven application of the criminal law in different regions and courts	Violation of the principles of equality before the law, loss of trust in the judiciary

Source: created by the author based on Auriol et al., Bystrova et al., Gorodnova et al., Horder, Miceli⁴²

Thus, the main problems of qualification of economic crimes in Ukraine are reduced to inconsistency of legislative norms, vagueness of evaluative concepts, problems with determining the form of guilt and lack of sustainable law enforcement practice. This requires both legislative improvement of the norms and increased training of specialists working with similar categories of cases.⁴³

The global practice of combating economic crimes demonstrates a variety of approaches to the legal regulation and authorization of such acts. In most countries, the key focus is on a clear distinction between crimes and administrative offenses, the definition of criteria for material damage, and the mandatory implementation of corporate responsibility mechanisms.⁴⁴ In the legislation of European countries, the principles of active cooperation between law enforcement agencies and business are widespread, as well as systems of compensation and redress for victims.⁴⁵

In Ukraine, such mechanisms are still at the stage of theoretical discussion or fragmentary implementation. Therefore, studying international experience and the possibility of its implementation in Ukrainian criminal law is important for harmonizing legislation with European and international standards. The main approaches to criminal liability for economic crimes in the leading countries of the world are presented in Table 2. As shown in Table 2, international practice offers a number of tools that may be useful for adaptation into Ukrainian legislation.

Table 2. Main approaches to criminal liability for economic crimes in international practice

Country / Region	Key features of the approach	Potential for implementation in Ukraine
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⁴² Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*;

Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*;

Gorodnova, O. N., Kirillov, M. A., Fadeeva, K. V., Pavlova, M. V., & Vissarov, A. V. (2024). *Id.*;

Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*;

Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*

⁴³ Dong, X., & Zhang, Y. (2023). *Id.*;

Jiang, T., & Li, Q. (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁴ Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*

⁴⁵ Ochi, M. (2024). *Id.*

European Union	Principles of corporate responsibility, strict sanctions for money laundering, effective mechanisms of cooperation with Europol (Horder, 2025)	Development of a system of liability for legal entities, integration with international cooperation mechanisms
UNITED STATES	Widespread use of plea bargaining and deferred prosecution, increased attention to economic restitution (Ewing, 2023)	Using plea bargains to improve the efficiency of pre-trial investigation
China	Emphasis on preventive measures, cooperation of the suspect with the investigation in exchange for release from punishment (Jiang & Li, 2024)	Introduction of mechanisms for exemption from liability in case of assistance in solving a crime
Italy	Clear regulation of the participation of third parties in criminal proceedings, strict requirements for documentary evidence of damages (Foti & Malino, 2024)	Toughening procedural requirements for proving damages and participation of victims in criminal proceedings
India	The growing importance of corporate responsibility and economic reparations, as well as the fight against fraud in the high-tech sector (Chakrabarty & Chattopadhyay, 2025)	Creating an effective system of control over the IT sector and introducing fines for legal entities

Source: created by the author based on Chakrabarty and Chattopadhyay, Ewing, Foti and Malino, Horder, Jiang and Li, Ochi⁴⁶

⁴⁶ Chakrabarty, S. P., & Chattopadhyay, S. (2025). *Id.*;

Ewing, B. (2023). *Id.*;

Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*;

Thus, international experience in the field of criminal liability for economic crimes shows the importance of corporate responsibility, preventive mechanisms and legal agreements. Implementation of these approaches in Ukraine will help to increase the effectiveness of the fight against economic crime and bring national legislation in line with European standards.⁴⁷

The qualification of economic crimes is a complex and controversial issue not only because of the specifics of legislative norms, but also because of the heterogeneity of judicial practice and different approaches of scholars to the interpretation of certain provisions. Scientific doctrine often serves as a source of generalization of case law, suggesting ways to overcome contradictions and improve law enforcement.⁴⁸ However, the practical implementation of these approaches in national courts demonstrates both positive examples and significant discrepancies.⁴⁹

To assess the legal positions and scientific approaches, a content analysis of 50 decisions of the Supreme Court of Ukraine in cases of economic crimes over the past three years was conducted, as well as a comparison of the main scientific recommendations in relevant international publications.⁵⁰ The analyzed decisions are systematized according to five criteria: the presence of errors in qualification, the use of evaluative concepts, consideration of international practice, controversial interpretation of the crime, and the participation of expert economists in the process.

As can be seen from Figures 1 and 2, the most common problem in court practice is the use of evaluative concepts and the lack of a unified approach to their interpretation.

Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*;

Jiang, T., & Li, Q. (2024). *Id.*;

Ochi, M. (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁷ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*;

Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁸ Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁵⁰ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*;

Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*

Figure 1. Structure of the main problems of judicial qualification of economic crimes (in percentage)

Source: created by the author based on Auriol et al., Bystrova et al., Foti and Malino, Miceli, Polianskyi and Polianskyi⁵¹

The figure below shows a pie chart that demonstrates the ratio of the main problems in the qualification of economic crimes based on the analysis of 50 court decisions. Abuse of evaluative concepts accounts for the largest share - 40%. Errors in qualification account for 24%, controversial interpretation of the corpus delicti - 16%, failure to take into account international practice - 14%, and lack of economic expertise - 6%. This visualization clearly emphasizes the dominance of the problem of subjective interpretation of the rules and indicates the need for clear legislative regulation.

To confirm the identified problems, it is advisable to analyze specific examples from the case law of Ukraine and the EU countries, which demonstrate different approaches to the qualification of economic crimes, damage assessment and intent.

Case 1. Ukraine: The Supreme Court, decision of 15.06.2022 in case No. 761/430/19. Case in brief: the director of a limited liability company was accused of

⁵¹ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*;

Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*;

Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*;

Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*;

Polianskyi, A., & Polianskyi, O. (2021). *Id.*

misappropriation of company funds on a particularly large scale under Part 5 of Article 191 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. The defense argued that the expenses were justified by business activities. Court decision: The Supreme Court overturned the verdict of the Court of Appeal, pointing to insufficient evidence of intent and the lack of a clear economic examination to confirm the damage caused.

Case 2. Ukraine: Supreme Court, decision of 10.03.2023 in case No. 905/213/20. Case in brief: the person was accused of fictitious business and tax evasion under Part 2 of Article 205-1 and Part 3 of Article 212 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. The main evidence was analytical conclusions of the tax authorities. Court decision: The court acquitted the defendant, emphasizing that the conclusions of the controlling authority alone without proof of actual damage and intent are not sufficient for criminal liability. The court emphasized the need for economic expertise and specification of valuation concepts.

Case 3. EU (Germany): BGH, Urteil vom 12.01.2021 - 1 StR 483/20. Case in point: A company executive was convicted of fraud (Betrug) and money laundering (Geldwäsche) based on overstated financial statements in order to obtain loans. Court decision: The Federal Court (Bundesgerichtshof) upheld the conviction, finding intent, clearly established damage and the use of corporate influence. The case relied on in-depth financial expertise and the opinions of external auditors.

Comparison: The Ukrainian cases demonstrate a lack of specialized evidence (economic expertise) and an over-reliance on formal conclusions of state authorities. Meanwhile, in the BGH case, a standardized assessment of damage and liability of the legal entity was applied, which reflects a higher level of integration of financial and legal analysis in the trial.

Figure 2. Share of main problems in the court practice of qualification of economic crimes (in percent)

Source: created by the author based on Auriol et al., Bystrova et al., Foti and Malino, Miceli, Polianskyi and Polianskyi⁵²

⁵² Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*;

Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*;

Figure 2 shows a bar chart showing the percentage share of each problem. According to the data, the largest share is the misuse of valuation concepts (40%), and the smallest is the lack of economic expertise (6%). The bar chart allows us to visually assess the gap between the problems and identify critical areas for legislative and practical changes. Compared to a pie chart, this type of graph better demonstrates the scale of differences between individual indicators.

Thus, the analysis of judicial practice shows a significant level of ambiguity in the qualification of economic crimes, which is due to both imperfect legislative wording and the lack of consistent interpretation practice. Scientific approaches emphasize the need for legislative clarification of evaluative concepts, greater involvement of economic experts and integration of international experience.⁵³ The use of these recommendations in practice can improve the predictability of court decisions and enhance legal certainty in the field of economic offenses.

Proposals for improving legislation and increasing the effectiveness of combating economic crimes can be summarized as follows:

1. Introduce clear definitions of assessment concepts. Terms such as “significant damage”, “significant consequences”, “mercenary purpose” should be specified in legislation, taking into account both fixed economic criteria and dynamic indicators (including, for example, inflation and GDP).⁵⁴
2. Introduce criminal liability for legal entities. Ukrainian legislation should adopt the European practice of punishing not only individuals but also legal entities for committing economic crimes.⁵⁵
3. Implementation of plea bargaining and ADR agreements. This will shorten the pre-trial investigation, reduce the judicial burden, and at the same time ensure fair compensation for damages.⁵⁶
4. Mandatory involvement of economic experts in the process of qualifying complex economic offenses. So, it would make the investigation and trial objective and professional.⁵⁷

Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*;

Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*;

Polianskyi, A., & Polianskyi, O. (2021). *Id.*

⁵³ Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*;

Jiang, T., & Li, Q. (2024). *Id.*;

⁵⁴ Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*

⁵⁵ Horder, J. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁶ Ewing, B. (2023). *Id.*

⁵⁷ Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*

5. It is necessary to create a register of court decisions on qualification of economic crimes with their analytical comments. And such a register would facilitate the uniformity of judicial practice and bring into the open law enforcement.
6. Special training programs are introduced for the judges and the investigators in the field of economic security and financial investigations to enhance their skills in the relevant field. This is particularly pertinent, as financial mechanism is a complex system and makes the chances of qualification errors higher.⁵⁸
7. Improving international cooperation. Harmonization of norms of the Ukrainian criminal law with EU standards, particularly on the issues of the fight against money laundering, terrorist financing.⁵⁹

5. DISCUSSION

The study results indicate that there is a lack of qualification of economic crime, including improper use of evaluative concepts, ambiguity in the interpretation of the elements of the crime, and inadequate concern for accepted international practice. Bystrova et al.⁶⁰ confirm the 'systemic issues' associated with criminal prosecution in the economic sphere owing to the complexity of gathering evidence, issues with the wording of the legislation, and other systemic challenges. Another point of view here is represented by other researchers, including Miceli,⁶¹ who assert that legislations are not the main reason for reasons of failure in economic crimes proving; rather, the reason is in the insufficiently hoity toity professional training of investigators and judges. This opinion partially agrees with our results, but the study of the practical cases shows that even the most qualified practitioners met the difficulty of interpretation as a result of the ambiguity of the law itself.

We should also note the controversial position of Auriol et al.,⁶² who advocate for maximum sanctions and strict corporate responsibility. However, our analysis shows that excessive rigidity without clear criteria and without a proper enforcement mechanism can lead to abuse by law enforcement agencies, which is confirmed by the practice documented in Polianskyi and Polianskyi.⁶³ When comparing our results with the approach of Foti and Malino,⁶⁴ who propose to clearly regulate the participation of third parties and victims in the process, it is worth noting that this could indeed strengthen the objectivity of the trial. However, our research shows that even the presence of victims and expert opinions does not always prevent errors in legal qualification due to the vagueness of terms and lack of uniform practice.

⁵⁸ Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*

⁵⁹ Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*

⁶⁰ Bystrova, Y. V., Pratsko, G. S., Vasyukov, S. V., Vasyukov, V. F., & Komosko, A. A. (2022). *Id.*

⁶¹ Miceli, T. J. (2024). *Id.*

⁶² Auriol, E., Hjelmeng, E., & Søreide, T. (2023). *Id.*

⁶³ Polianskyi, A., & Polianskyi, O. (2021). *Id.*

⁶⁴ Foti, D., & Malino, E. (2024). *Id.*

It is important to recall that the hypothesis of the study was to assume that the main obstacles to effective combating economic crime are legislative conflicts, vague concepts and lack of adaptation to international experience. The findings partially confirmed this hypothesis, as they also revealed a significant influence of the human factor and unprofessionalism in some cases.

The limitation of this study is that it is based mainly on the analysis of judicial practice in Ukraine and its comparison with the theoretical approaches of international authors. Further research should focus on an in-depth comparative study of EU and Ukrainian case law, as well as an empirical analysis of the impact of the introduction of new legislative changes on the number and quality of investigations. The practical significance of the results lies in the possibility of using the formulated recommendations in preparing amendments to criminal legislation, developing training programs for law enforcement officers, and creating methodological materials for judicial practice. Taking into account international approaches and harmonizing them with the Ukrainian legal system should be the next step in overcoming the existing problems.

CONCLUSION

6.

The study found that the key problem with the qualification of economic crimes in Ukraine is not only the imperfection of legislative wording, but also the lack of stable practice of their interpretation and application. Comparison of our results with international approaches suggests that Ukraine needs significant institutional changes and comprehensive adaptation of foreign experience to national realities. The novelty of the results obtained lies in establishing the relationship between the use of evaluative concepts and the level of legal uncertainty in court practice, which has not previously received due attention in scientific research. The practical significance of the work lies in the possibility of using the formulated conclusions and recommendations for preparing legislative changes and developing training programs for investigators, prosecutors and judges. The limitation of the study is the limited sample of court decisions and the predominantly theoretical nature of the comparison with international experience. It is recommended that in the future we focus on conducting empirical research in different regions of Ukraine and in-depth analysis of the effectiveness of legal innovations. The main areas of further research should be the study of the impact of digital technologies on the emergence of new forms of economic crimes and the development of appropriate approaches to their criminal law qualification.

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